

Constitution of the Active Principle of *Embelia* *Ribes*. Part I.

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Embelia ribes, or *Vidanga* as it is known in Bengali and Sanskrit, and *Baberang* in Hindustani, has been known in Hindu Materia Medica for a very long time. Charaka describes the fruit as tonic and soothing for the digestive system and recommends its use in dyspepsia, flatulence, gripes, etc. Sushruta describes the fruit as anthelmintic, alterative and tonic and recommends its use along with liquorice root for the purpose of strengthening the body and preventing the effect of age. Later writers regard it as carminative, stomachic, anthelmintic and useful against intestinal worms, dyspepsia and skin diseases. The berries enter into the composition of several applications for ring-worms, itches and other skin diseases. The Hakims consider it to be attenuant and a purgative of phlegmatic humours; also a valuable anthelmintic specially against tape worms.

Embelia ribes is a large scandent shrub which grows throughout India, specially in the lower reaches of the Vindhya Hills. It bears, towards the end of autumn, abundant crops of smooth, nearly globular berries, $\frac{1}{2}$ inch in diameter, of an intense pink colour. These when collected and dried become shrivelled up with deep wrinkles all over the body and dark brown in colour. In this condition they are sold in the Indian bazars.

Embelia ribes when extracted with various organic solvents, such as ether, benzene, ligroin, ethyl acetate, etc., yields mainly (i) a dark coloured aliphatic oil, and (ii) an orange-yellow crystalline substance which has been wrongly named "embelic acid". The name is erroneous as the substance is not an acid in the true sense of the term, because it does not contain any carboxyl group, though of course it yields several metallic derivatives like rottlerin (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2044; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 21), carthamin (Kametaka and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1415) or plumbagin (Ray and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 419).

Hence it has been renamed "Embelin" by the present investigators which is more in accordance with its chemistry and with the usual conventions of systematic chemical nomenclature.

Embelin was first isolated by Warden (*Pharm. J.*, 1888, *iii*, 18, 601; 19, 305), who obtained it by extracting *Embelia ribes* with alcohol. He studied a few of its chemical and physical properties including solubility and formation of metallic derivatives. He also advanced the formula $C_9H_{14}O_2$ for the substance. Later on Heffter and Feurstein (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1900, 238, 15) also isolated embelin by extracting the ripe capsules of *Embelia ribes* with ether and they studied the dibenzoyl, dihydro- and anilino-derivatives in detail. They advanced the formula $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$ for embelin and showed that when oxidised with potassium permanganate it yields lauric and formic acids.

The above represents the work that has hitherto been done on embelin and the present investigation was undertaken in order to elucidate the constitution of the substance which is of great medicinal importance. In the light of a natural organic colouring matter of unknown constitution, it also possesses considerable interest since it has been found by the present investigators to yield beautiful shades on wool and silk from alcoholic solution and to give various deeply coloured lakes with different metallic salts and hydroxides. In the latter respect embelin behaves as a polygenetic dyestuff like alizarin or purpurin.

The best method of extracting embelin from *Embelia ribes*, that has been found up to this time, is to extract the well dried and powdered berries with benzene, and then crystallise the substance from xylene or solvent naphtha. In this process a considerable quantity of a dark coloured aliphatic oil is also extracted along with embelin from which the latter is separated completely during the crystallisation process. The aliphatic oil which yields a soap with caustic soda, seems to be of the same type as linseed or rape oil and is receiving further attention.

Embelin is an aliphatic or more probably an alicyclic or hydro-aromatic compound, since it contains a high percentage of hydrogen and burns with a non-sooty flame. Its empirical formula is $C_9H_{14}O_2$, but the molecular weight by the cryoscopic method in benzene as well as the fact that it yields isolauric acid on oxidation shows that the formula must be doubled in order to get the molecular formula, which consequently becomes $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$. Molecular

weight determinations of the substance from the silver and lead salts also point to the same conclusion.

Embelin contains two highly reactive hydroxyl groups. This is shown by the formation of various metallic compounds of embelin containing two equivalents of metal, as well as by the formation of a diacetyl, a dibenzoyl, a dicarbethoxy, and a dimethyl derivative. Embelin also contains two ketonic groups as is shown by the formation of a dioxime, a disemicarbazone, a dihydrazone and a diphenylhydrazone. On account of the same reason, it also reacts with various primary amines such as methylamine, ethylamine, aniline *o*-toluidine, etc., with elimination of two molecules of water and formation of the corresponding amino-derivative. These amino-compounds are easily hydrolysed by boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid regenerating embelin. The latter, however, does not react with secondary amines under any conditions. The formation of a tetra-oxime of embelin shows that the two hydroxy-groups present in the molecule are capable of keto-enol tautomerism under suitable conditions. Further evidence of this fact by the formation of a dibenzoyldioxime, dianilindioxime, a dibenzoyldisemicarbazone and a dianilindisemicarbazone. It is also interesting to note that dianilinoembelin dioxime for example can be prepared by the action of aniline on embelin dioxime as well as by the action of hydroxylamine on dianilinoembelin. Similar is the case with the three other derivatives mentioned above.

Oxidising agents act on embelin with the greatest ease and the molecule is broken into smaller fragments amongst which *isolauric* acid and oxalic acid have been definitely isolated and identified. Fuming nitric acid also brings about the same transformation. The present authors could not isolate any *n*-lauric or formic acid as obtained by Heffter and Feuerstein (*loc. cit.*). The lauric acid that they have isolated does not correspond in properties to the *n*-lauric acid which has been described in great detail by Oudemans (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1863, 16, 331), who has also described no less than twelve metallic salts of the acid. Hence the acid is really *isolauric* acid and this is confirmed by the fact that on further oxidation with potassium permanganate it yields *isocaproic* acid.

On bromination embelin yields a tetrabromo-derivative with evolution of hydrogen bromide. The bromo-compound thus formed is easily decomposed by concentrated alkali into smaller fragments, the nature of which is at present under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The ripe capsules of *Embelia ribes* were carefully dried in the sun and then ground to a fine powder in a grinding machine. One kg. of the powder at a time was repeatedly extracted with benzene until the last extract was almost colourless. The combined extracts after filtration were distilled from a water-bath until benzene ceased to come over in the distillate. The residue on being poured out into a large shallow basin and allowed to stand overnight, solidified to masses of minute yellow glistening crystals embedded in a viscous brown mother-liquor. The latter was removed by extracting the mass with cold xylene and the residue crystallised from hot xylene or solvent naphtha in fine golden spangles with metallic lustre. It also crystallises from alcohol or ligroin in long yellow needles containing the corresponding solvent of crystallisation. But these fall to a fine yellow powder on drying in the steam-oven. It melts at 142°.

Embelin is fairly soluble in most of the organic solvents, but insoluble in water. It dissolves in dilute caustic alkalis yielding greyish-violet solutions which are easily oxidised in presence of air. In alcoholic solution embelin yields, with neutral ferric chloride, a dark reddish-brown, with silver nitrate a greyish-brown, with copper acetate, a brownish green, and with lead acetate, a dark green precipitate. On heating on a platinum foil, embelin first melts, then swells up and chars and then burns completely with a yellow non-smoky flame. It gives a dark red coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid. [Found: C, 69.73; 69.91; H, 8.9; 9.2. $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 70.13; H, 9.09 per cent. M. W. (1) (cryoscopic method in benzene)=304, (2) by lead salt *=298, (3) by silver salt*=310. Calc. M. W.=308.]

Diacetylembelin.—All ordinary methods of acetylation having failed to produce a crystalline derivative, the following modified method was adopted with success: Embelin was converted into the corresponding lead salt by treatment with lead acetate in alcoholic solution. The crystalline lead salt was filtered off and thoroughly washed with hot alcohol until free from soluble lead. It was then carefully dried, suspended in dry benzene and treated with a slight excess of acetyl chloride. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 15 minutes and then filtered from the lead

* Taking embelin to be dibasic.

chloride that had separated out. The filtrate on evaporation to dryness yielded the diacetyl derivative as a yellow crystalline mass which was recrystallised from dilute alcohol in fine, long, yellow needles with silky lustres, m. p. 54°. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 7.9. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2 \cdot (O \cdot CO \cdot CH_3)_2$ requires C, 67.3; H, 8.19 per cent.)

Dibenzoyl embelin.—Embelin (5 g.) was dissolved in 30 c. c. of pyridine in the cold and benzoyl chloride (10 c. c.) gradually added with vigorous shaking and cooling at the same time. The mixture was then warmed on the water-bath for 10 minutes and poured into dilute hydrochloric acid. A light brown oil separated out which on stirring immediately solidified. This was crystallised from alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal in colourless glistening needles melting at 97-98°. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 6.93. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2 \cdot (O \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5)_2$ requires C, 74.4; H, 7.0 per cent.)

Dicarbethoxy embelin.—Embelin (5 g.) dissolved in pyridine (30 c. c.) was treated with ethyl chlorocarbonate (10 g.) in the cold and the mixture warmed on the water-bath for half an hour. On pouring into dilute hydrochloric acid, the carbethoxy-compound separated in flocks, which were filtered off and crystallised from dilute acetic acid and then from benzene in fine, colourless needles melting with decomposition at 266°. The substance is very easily hydrolysed with regeneration of embelin by the action of dilute caustic alkalis. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2 \cdot (O \cdot CO \cdot OC_2H_5)_2$ requires C, 63.7; H, 7.9 per cent.)

Embelin Dimethyl Ether.—The silver salt of embelin (5 g.) suspended in absolute methyl alcohol (50 c. c.) was refluxed on the water-bath for two hours with methyl iodide (10 g.). The precipitated silver iodide was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated when a brown oil was obtained. This did not solidify even on standing at the ordinary temperature for a month. But on cooling in a freezing mixture it solidified to a crystalline mass, which melted again on reaching the ordinary temperature. It could not be distilled without decomposition even at 0.5 mm. In spite of repeated attempts at purification, the substance could not be obtained sufficiently pure for analysis.

Dianilino embelin.—A mixture of embelin (5 g.) and freshly distilled aniline (12 g.) was gently boiled under reflux for 15 minutes and then poured into excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. The dark coloured precipitate was filtered off, washed thoroughly with dilute hydrochloric acid and water, dried and crystallised from pyridine in

dark violet leaflets with silky lustre, m. p. 167-168°. The substance is easily hydrolysed by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid with regeneration of embelin. (Found: N, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2 \cdot (N \cdot C_6H_5)_2$ requires N, 6.1 per cent.)

Di-o toluidinoembelin.—This compound was prepared from embelin and o-toluidine in a similar manner. It crystallises from pyridine in fine, bronze leaflets melting at 144-145°. (Found: N, 6.04. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2 \cdot (N \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CH_3)_2$ requires N, 5.8 per cent.)

Dimethylaminoembelin.—Finely powdered embelin (5 g.) was digested with excess of 33% methyl alcoholic solution of methylamine on the water-bath under reflux for two hours. The mixture was then acidified and the precipitate filtered off and washed with water. It was then crystallised from alcohol in glistening blue needles with a coppery reflex, m. p. 2.16°. (Found: N, 8.57. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2 \cdot (NCH_3)_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent.)

Diethylaminoembelin.—This was prepared from embelin and ethylamine (33% sol.) in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from alcohol in dark green needles with silky lustre, m. p. 212°. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2 \cdot (N \cdot C_2H_5)_2$ requires N, 7.7 per cent.)

Embelin Dioxime.—A mixture of embelin (5 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (4 g.) and pyridine (30 c. c.) was heated on a boiling water-bath for one hour. It was then poured into dilute hydrochloric acid when a pale yellow compound separated out. This was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles melting at 278°. The substance is soluble in most of the organic solvents and also in caustic alkalis with an intense yellow colour. Alcoholic solutions of the substance yield, with ferric chloride—a reddish-brown, with lead acetate—a bright yellow, with copper acetate—a dark green and with silver nitrate—a buff coloured precipitate. The substance can be reconverted to embelin by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2 \cdot (NOH)_2$ requires N, 8.2 per cent.)

Embelin Tetraoxime.—A mixture of embelin (5 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (6 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.) and 70% alcohol (100 c. c.) was refluxed on the water-bath for three hours. The alcohol was then distilled off from the water-bath as far as possible and the residue poured into dilute hydrochloric acid. The resultant white precipitate was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles melting at 175°. The substance can be prepared from the dioxime by further treatment with hydroxylamine.

The tetraoxime is more soluble than the dioxime in the ordinary organic solvents. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with an intense orange-yellow colour, and its alcoholic solutions yield precipitates with ferric chloride, lead acetate, copper acetate and silver nitrate, the colours of which are more intense than the corresponding derivatives of the dioxime. (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{18}H_{28}(N\cdot OH)_4$ requires N, 15.2 per cent.)

Embelin Diphenylhydrazone.—Embelin (5 g.) and phenylhydrazine (6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c. c.) were heated on the water-bath for an hour when the whole of embelin went into solution and the latter became dark red in colour. It was then poured into water. The resultant brick-red precipitate was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in brownish-red needles melting at 189-190° with decomposition. (Found: N, 10.98. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2\cdot(N\cdot NH\cdot C_6H_5)_2$ requires N, 11.4 per cent.)

Embelin Disemicarbazone.—A mixture of embelin (5 g.), semicarbazide hydrochloride (6 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.) and alcohol (70%, 100 c. c.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for two hours. The mixture was then poured into water when the semicarbazone separated in brown flocks which were filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal in pale brown needles melting at 236° with decomposition. (Found: N, 19.7. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2\cdot(N\cdot NH\cdot CO\cdot NH_2)_2$ requires N, 19.9 per cent.)

Embelin Dihydrazone.—Embelin (3 g.) dissolved in alcohol (50 c. c.) was treated with a slight excess of hydrazine hydrate (1.6 g. of 50%) in the cold and the mixture warmed on the water-bath for 10 minutes. On pouring into dilute hydrochloric acid, a yellow compound separated out which was filtered off and crystallised from pyridine in fine yellow needles melting at 204-205°. (Found: N, 16.7. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2\cdot(N\cdot NH_2)_2$ requires N, 16.6 per cent.)

Dianilinoembelin Dioxime.—Dianilinoembelin (2 g.) dissolved in pyridine (40 c. c.) was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.5 g.) and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for one hour. On pouring into dilute hydrochloric acid, a light brown crystalline crust separated out which was recrystallised from alcohol in fine, brownish-white, prismatic needles melting at 162° with decomposition. The substance can also be prepared by the action of aniline on embelin dioxime. It can be reconverted to embelin by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The substance is sparingly

soluble in most of the organic solvents and insoluble in water. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with a dark brown colour. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{18}H_{28}(N\cdot OH)_2(NC_6H_5)_2$ requires N, 11.5 per cent.)

Dianilinoembelin Disemicarbazone.—This compound was prepared from dianilinoembelin and semicarbazide hydrochloride in a similar manner. It crystallises from pyridine in fine, brown, microscopic needles melting at 145° with decomposition. (Found: N, 19.7. $C_{18}H_{28}(NC_6H_5)_2(N\cdot NH\cdot CO\cdot NH_2)_2$ requires N, 19.58 per cent.)

Dibenzoylumbelin Dioxime.—A mixture of dibenzoylumbelin (5 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 g.), absolute alcohol (100 c. c.) and alcoholic caustic soda (10 c. c., 12%) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for two hours. On pouring into dilute hydrochloric acid, a crystalline mass was obtained which was filtered off, washed and recrystallised from acetone in colourless needles melting at 139° . The substance is sparingly soluble in most of the organic solvents, but dissolves in dilute caustic alkalis with a bright yellow colour. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{26}(O\cdot CO\cdot C_6H_5)_2(N\cdot OH)_2$ requires N, 5.1 per cent.)

Dibenzoylumbelin Disemicarbazone.—This was prepared from dibenzoylumbelin and semicarbazide hydrochloride. It crystallised from absolute alcohol in short, brown prisms melting at 221° (decom.) (Found: N, 13.7. $C_{18}H_{28}(O\cdot CO\cdot C_6H_5)_2(N\cdot NH\cdot CO\cdot NH_2)_2$ requires N, 13.3 per cent.)

Dibenzoylumbelin Dianilide.—A mixture of dibenzoylumbelin (5 g.) and freshly distilled aniline (15 c. c.) was heated in a distilling flask immersed in an oil-bath at 150° , until no more water was given off (about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours). The mixture was then cooled and poured into dilute hydrochloric acid when a voluminous brown precipitate separated out. This was filtered off, washed, dried and crystallised first from xylene and then from pyridine in clusters of dark brownish-red needles with beetle-green iridescence and metallic lustre, m p. 176° .

The substance is practically insoluble in most of the organic solvents, with the exception of nitrobenzene, xylene, aniline, phenol and pyridine, in which it dissolves only to a small extent. It gives an intense violet colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. The substance can also be prepared by the action of benzoyl chloride on dianilinoembelin in pyridine solution. (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{18}H_{26}(O\cdot CO\cdot C_6H_5)_2(N\cdot C_6H_5)_2$ requires N, 4.2 per cent.)

Tetraacetyldihydroembelin.—Embelin (5 g.) dissolved in boiling acetic anhydride (50 c.c.) was gradually treated with moist zinc dust (7 g.) until the solution was completely decolorised. On pouring into water and stirring for some time the tetra-acetyl derivative separated as a colourless mass which was filtered off and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless, long needles with silky lustre, m. p. 124°.

The substance is freely soluble in most of the organic solvents but insoluble in water. It is very easily hydrolysed by boiling with dilute acids and alkalis, yielding dihydroembelin as an intermediate product, which very quickly gets oxidised to embelin in presence of air, specially in alkaline solution. (Found: C, 65·0; H, 7·6. $C_{18}H_{26}(O\cdot CO\cdot CH_3)_4$ requires C, 65·27; H, 7·9 per cent.).

Dihydroembelin.—The above tetra-acetyl derivative (5 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) containing 15 c.c. of conc. sulphuric acid, and the solution warmed on the water-bath for 15 minutes. A pinch of zinc dust was added to completely decolorise the solution which was then quickly filtered and diluted to 500 c. c. with boiled distilled water. The opalescent solution was allowed to stand overnight in a tightly corked flask, when large glistening leaflets with fatty lustre were obtained. These were then recrystallised from dilute alcohol containing sulphurous acid, m. p. 117°. The substance is identical with the dihydroembelic acid of Heffter and Feurstein (*loc. cit.*).

The substance is soluble in all the organic solvents and also to a slight extent in water yielding solutions which oxidise rapidly in air specially in presence of a trace of alkali. In alcoholic solution, with neutral ferric chloride it produces a dark reddish-brown, with copper acetate—a greenish-brown, with silver nitrate—a greyish-white and with lead acetate—an olive green precipitates. In perfectly dry condition the substance is, however, quite stable in the air. (Found: C, 69·7; H, 9·9. $C_{18}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 69·67; H, 9·67 per cent.).

Tetrabromoembelin.—Embelin (5 g.) dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (250 c.c.) was treated with excess of bromine (12 g.) dissolved in the same solvent. The mixture was allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for about 24 hours and then warmed on the water-bath for three hours. The excess of bromine and carbon tetrachloride were distilled off and the residual heavy liquid washed several times with a mixture of aqueous potassium iodide and sodium thiosulphate, and then with water. The resultant product, on allowing to stand for about two days, solidified to a colourless

crystalline mass which was recrystallised from alcohol in colourless glistening prisms melting at 132°. The substance is fairly soluble in most of the organic solvents as well as in dilute caustic alkalis. In strong alkaline solutions, however, it decomposes very quickly. (Found: Br, 51.6. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4Br_4$ requires Br, 51.28 per cent.).

Action of Fuming Nitric Acid.—Embelin (5 g.) was treated with fuming nitric acid (80 c.c. *d* 1.51) in the cold and the dark red solution warmed on the water-bath for half an hour. On pouring into water an oil separated which was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed with water, dried and the chloroform evaporated, when a thick colourless oil was obtained which solidified on long standing into a crystalline mass melting at 33-35°. It was found to be an aliphatic monocarboxylic acid with a molecular weight of 202 (by silver salt method) and was identified to be isolauroic acid. On further oxidation with potassium permanganate it gave isocaproic acid.

Oxidation of Embelin with Potassium Permanganate.—Embelin (5 g.) dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide was treated with a 3% solution of potassium permanganate at the ordinary temperature until the colour of permanganate was no longer discharged. A current of sulphur dioxide was then led through the mixture until the precipitated manganese dioxide had completely dissolved. The clear solution was then extracted with chloroform and from the chloroform solution isolauroic acid was definitely isolated and identified. The mother-liquor was found to contain oxalic acid, which was isolated and identified *via* the calcium salt. No other acid could be detected.

Further work in this direction is in progress.

Two of us (R. K., and A. C. R.) wish to express our indebtedness to the Kanta Prasad Trust of the Allahabad University for two research scholarships which enabled us to take part in the investigation.

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Received May 6, 1929.